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Diversity of Woody Flora around two Apiaries in the Badenou Protected Forest (Northern Côte d'Ivoire)

Author's Details :

Dofoung KONE^{1,2*}, **Eboua Narcisse WANDAN**¹, **Noufou Doudjo OUATTARA**^{3,4}, **Bruno Marcel IRITIE**⁵
¹Laboratoire Sciences Société & Environnement, Institut National Polytechnique Félix Houphouët-Boigny, Yamoussoukro, Côte d'Ivoire ²Institut de Gestion Agropastorale, Université Peleforo Gon Coulibaly, Korhogo, Côte d'Ivoire ³UFR Sciences de la Nature, Université Nangui Abrogoua d'Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire ⁴Centre Suisse de Recherche Scientifique en Côte d'Ivoire, Côte d'Ivoire ⁵Laboratoire de Zootechnie, Institut National Polytechnique Félix Houphouët-Boigny, Yamoussoukro, Côte d'Ivoire
*Correspondence, email: agrodof41@yahoo.fr / Tel (+225) 47 45 10 66

Received Date: 23-Oct-2019

Accepted Date: 17-Nov-2020

Published Date: 29-Feb-2020

Abstract

This study aimed at analyzing the floristic diversity of the woody vegetation around two experimental apiaries installed in the Badenou classified forest. A surface survey was carried out and the number of species, genera, families, Shannon, and Piélou indices were determined. The similarity coefficients of Jaccard and Sorensen were calculated to compare the two sites. An average floristic richness was observed with 96 species grouped into 72 genera and 30 families. The Shannon and Piélou indices were found to be 3.76 and 0.82 respectively. Except the Piélou index, all the determined floristic diversity parameters varied significantly according to the type of vegetation. Thus, the species richness varies from 7.50 ± 2.12 in grass savannah to 21.14 ± 7.06 in open forest; the number of families from 5.50 ± 2.12 in grass savannah to 11.57 ± 4.28 in opens forest, and the Shannon index of 1.57 ± 0.67 in grassy savannah at 2.40 ± 0.42 in open forest. Both sites have the same floristic background. The determination of melliferous species around these apiaries is in progress but these results indicated that the diversity of woody species is a major asset for beekeeping because it is likely to provide the floral resources necessary for a large production of honey.

Keywords: Inventory, woody flora, floristic diversity, apiary, classified forest

INTRODUCTION

From the early years of its independence, the State of Côte d'Ivoire has taken various measures to restore forest cover and its sustainable management (Zadou *et al.*, 2011). Despite these measures, the country's forest ecosystems are degrading significantly due mainly to anthropogenic activity (N'guessan *et al.*, 2006). In fact, populations infiltrate protected forests to practice agriculture or collect medicinal plants (Kassi *et al.*, 2012). This way of using protected forest resources has led to their conversion into agricultural land which is incompatible with their sustainability.

This anthropogenic pressure is exerted on the humid dense forests of the south as well as on the mixed forest and grassland of the Sudanian zone of the north of the country. In the savannah zone of Côte d'Ivoire, several classified forests have been decommissioned, some have even disappeared and others are endangered (Ouattara, 2001). In this zone, the Badenou classified forest is one of the few with a good level of conservation (N'guessan *et al.*, 2006). However, it faces real and imminent risks since a survey conducted in 1992 as part of its management revealed that about 500 people occupied 1100 ha, or 4% of its total area (Affoué, 1995). In addition, the riparian populations of this classified forest, who have long practiced agriculture to satisfy their food needs, currently have diversified and growing agricultural productions. Their agricultural production is in fact the object of an increasingly important demand coming from the growing urban populations and the exporters of cotton and cashew nuts. As this growth in agricultural production is mainly due to an expansion of cultivated areas, this shift from subsistence agriculture to market farming entails competition between farmers for arable land.

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The current context of scarcity of agricultural land increases the risk of infiltration of this protected forest by farmers. It is therefore necessary to propose solutions that can encourage people to support its sustainable management. The development of beekeeping around this forest for the benefit of local populations seems to be an interesting economic prospect since it will enable population to benefit from this forest ecosystem without causing its degradation.

The importance of beekeeping for these populations is sufficiently obvious. In fact, beekeeping can improve their live hood through consumption and sale bee products (Peter, 2008). Honey, the main product of beekeeping, sells well in Côte d'Ivoire with a price currently ranging between 1000 and 3000 F CFA per kilogram (1 F CFA = 0.0015 Euro) (Ohoueu *et al.*, 2017). According to this study, the average net annual income of the surveyed beekeepers was 470 575 F CFA with an average annual production of 453.78 kg of honey and 48.18 kg of wax. Besides that, beekeeping contributes to the surrounding rural economy through crop pollination (Fohouo *et al.*, 2009), the enhancement of trade between beekeepers, honey and other bee products (wax, pollen, propolis) consumers, beekeeping equipment manufacturers and traders (beehives, smokers, protective clothing, packaging equipment, etc.); and the various intermediaries. Moreover, it is an activity that requires relatively few financial, material, and human resources. It can also be easily associated with other agricultural activities (Sokemawu, 2016). In fact, bees are collected from the wild and they gather their own food, equipment used for their rearing is made locally and it is not essential to own a land to practice of beekeeping.

The implementation of a major apiculture project requires a preliminary assessment of the potential of the area's honey. Among these potentialities, floristic assets stand out as it is well known that bee products reflect in quantity and quality the nature of honey plants (Balagueman *et al.*, 2017). The floristic and structural diversity of the vegetation then constitutes data whose knowledge is essential for the settlement of a sound beekeeping project. In Côte d'Ivoire and in several West and Central African countries, research has been done in this direction (Bakenga *et al.*, 2000; Nombé, 2003; Dongock *et al.*, 2004; Yédomonhan, 2009; Coulibaly, 2014; Iritié *et al.*, 2014). However, the assessment of the melliferous potential of classified forests in order to promote beekeeping for riparian populations and the sustainable management of these forest has not yet been under investigation in Côte d'Ivoire.

The present study aims to characterize the woody vegetation around two experimental apiaries installed in the Badenou classified forest through the analysis of its floristic diversity.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study site

Experimental setup

The inventory was made within 0.5 km around each of the two experimental apiaries previously installed in the classified forest. This corresponds to an area of 78.5 ha around each apiary which is 157 ha of observation area. The surface inventory method was adopted in rectangular plots of 200 x 200 m spaced 200 m apart around each apiary (Yédomonhan, 2009; Coulibaly, 2014) (Figure 2).

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Figure 1: Location of the study area

Figure 2: Distribution of survey plots in the Inventory area

Inventory

The inventory was conducted in December 2017. In each inventory plot, all woody plants were identified. On each individual, the diameter at breast height (dbh) was determined. The minimum diameter at breast height (dbh) chosen is 3 cm in order to take into account the majority of shrubs and small-diameter shrubs which, however, have reached the age of flowering and can therefore have a melliferous interest (Coulibaly, 2014).

Most plant species were identified *in situ*; those for whom the identification *in situ* was not possible, were sent to the herbarium of the CSRS for determination by comparing samples collected with old specimens

preserved in the herbarium. Identification catalogs (Aké-Assi, 2001 and 2002; Chatelain *et al.*, 2011), and the digital flora of Bonnet *et al.* (2005), and the online database of the Conservatory and Botanical Garden of the City of Geneva (<http://www.ville-ge.ch/musinfo/bd/cjb/africa/>) were also used for this purpose. The nomenclature used for this work was that of phylogenetic classification (APG IV, 2016).

Floristic diversity analysis

Floristic diversity was assessed using species richness (α -diversity), genera and family diversity, and Shannon and Piéluou indices. These diversity parameters were determined for each plot and for each apiary. The species richness or α -diversity of an environment is defined as the set of all the plant species encountered in this environment, regardless of their abundance and level of participation in the structure (Bouko *et al.*, 2007). The Shannon index (H') is given by the equation 1

$$H' = - \sum p_i \ln p_i \quad (1)$$

where $p_i = n_i/N$, with n_i the number of individuals of species i and N the sum of n_i .

Diversity is low when $H' < 3$, high when $H' = 4$ and average if H' is between 3 and 4 (Yédomonhan, 2009).

To reinforce the values produced by the Shannon index, the Piéluou equitability index (EH'), also called the equidistribution index, is often associated with it (Ouattara, 2017).

$$EH' = H' / H'_{max} = H' / \ln R \quad (2)$$

where R denotes the specific richness.

The value of EH' tends to 0 when almost all individuals belong to the same species and is equal to 1 when the individuals are equitably distributed among the different species encountered in the plot (Ouattara *et al.*, 2016).

Comparison of the flora of the two sites

To evaluate the degree of similarity between the two sites, the floristic data were compared using the similarity coefficients of Jaccard (Eq 3) and Sorensen (Eq 4) (Ouattara, 2017). The Jaccard coefficient gives the same rating to the presence or the absence of species while the Sorensen coefficient gives a double advantage to the presence of species (Kimpouni *et al.*, 2013).

$$IJ_{ac} = [c / (a + b - c)] \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$IS_{or} = [2c / (a + b)] \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where a is the specific richness of the first site, b is the specific richness of the second site and c is the number of species common to both sites.

The calculated values of these indices vary between 0% (when the two sites have no common species) and 100% (when the two sites are absolutely similar).

Statistical analysis of the data

The means of floristic parameters (number of species, genus and families, Shannon and Piéluou indices) were compared from one site to another and from one type of vegetation to another using one-way ANOVA with STATISTICA 7.1 software. The normality of the data and the homogeneity of the variances were previously verified using respectively the Shapiro-Wilk test and the Cochran, Hartley, Bartlett test. The significance was assessed at the 5% level (p -value ≤ 0.05) and when a significant difference was observed for a given parameter, the Fisher test was performed to distinguish the homogeneous groups.

RESULTS

Specific wealth, diversity in genres and families

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The floristic inventory around the two apiaries identified 96 ligneous species belonging to 72 genera and 30 botanical families. The richness of the flora around the Tiebila apiary was 71 species grouped into 62 genera. Concerning the site of Nafoun, 76 species in 56 genera were identified. On each site, the identified species are distributed in 27 botanical families. The average species richness, the average number of genus and the number of families according to the sites showed non-significant difference (Table 1).

Table 1: Floristic diversity parameters determined at the inventory sites

Floristic Parameters		Sites			Statistics
		Nafoun	Tiébila	Nafoun and Tiébila	
Number of species	By plot	16,00 ± 5,97a	15,65 ± 4,70a	15,82 ± 5,31	F= 0,042 P= 0,838
	Total	76	71	96	
Number of genus	By plot	14,55 ± 4,92a	14,35 ± 4,38a	14,45 ± 4,60	F= 0,018 P= 0,893
	Total	56	62	72	
Number of families	By plot	8,65 ± 3,21a	8,90 ± 3,21a	8,77 ± 3,17	F= 0,061 P= 0,807
	Total	27	27	30	
Shannon Index (H')	By plot	2,21 ± 0,48a	2,20 ± 0,30a	2,21 ± 0,40	F= 0,003 P= 0,956
	Total	3,64	3,42	3,76	
Piélou Index (EH')	By plot	0,81 ± 0,09a	0,81 ± 0,08a	0,81 ± 0,08	F= 0,008 P= 0,928
	Total	0,84	0,80	0,82	

In each row, the assigned average values of the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% threshold (Fisher's test)

Concerning vegetation type, species richness varies from 7.50 ± 2.12 in grassland savannah to 21.14 ± 7.06 in open forest, the number of genera from 6.50 ± 0.71 in grassland savannah to 18.86 ± 5.81 in open forest and the number of families from 5.50 ± 2.12 in grass savannah to 11.57 ± 4.28 in open forest. These parameters are significantly different (Table 2).

Table 2: Floristic diversity parameters determined at the vegetation types

Floristic parameters		Vegetation types					Statistics
		Cleared forest	Wooded savannah	Treed savannah	Grassy savannah	Bush fallow	
Number of species	By plot	21,14 ± 7,06c	15,67 ± 3,98a	15,47 ± 3,56a	7,50 ± 2,12b	9,50 ± 0,71a,b	F= 5,386 P= 0,002
	Total	63	57	65	15	14	
Number of genus	By plot	18,86 ± 5,81c	14,33 ± 3,50b	14,35 ± 3,10b	6,50 ± 0,71a	8,50 ± 0,71a	F= 5,926 P= 0,001
	Total	52	47	51	13	11	
Number of families	By plot	11,57 ± 4,28b	8,75 ± 2,86a	8,35 ± 2,42a	5,50 ± 2,12a	6,00 ± 0,00a	F= 2,775 P= 0,042
	Total	23	23	23	9	8	
Shannon Index (H')	By plot	2,40 ± 0,42b	2,29 ± 0,39a,b	2,19 ± 0,30a,b	1,57 ± 0,67c	1,79 ± 0,23a,c	F= 2,831 P= 0,039
	Total	3,55	3,39	3,35	2,26	1,96	
Piélou Index (EH')	By plot	0,80 ± 0,06a	0,84 ± 0,11a	0,81 ± 0,07a	0,77 ± 0,23a	0,79 ± 0,07a	F= 0,412 P= 0,799
	Total	0,86	0,84	0,80	0,83	0,74	

In each row, the assigned average values of the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% threshold (Fisher's test)

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The results indicated that the most diversified genera are *Acacia* (6 species), *Ficus* (5 species), *Cissus* (3 species), *Combretum* (3 species), *Lansea* (3 species) and *Terminalia* (3 species). In total, 59 genera, or 81.94% of this taxa were monospecific and contain 61.46% of the species recorded. The richest family recorded was Fabaceae with 23 species, or 23.96% of the taxa (Figure 3). The 11 richest families recorded were Fabaceae (23 species, 23.96%), Rubiaceae (9 species, 9.38%), Combretaceae (8 species, 8.33%), Phyllanthaceae (7 species, 7.29%), Apocynaceae (5 species, 5.21%), Moraceae (5 species, 5.21%), Anacardiaceae (4 species, 4.17%), Lamiaceae (3 species, 3.13%), Meliaceae (3 species, 3.13%), Ochnaceae (3 species, 3.13%) and Vitaceae (3 species, 3.13%). These families alone account for 70 species representing 72.92% of this taxonomic level.

Shannon and Piélou Indices

The Shannon diversity index was 3.42 at the site of Tiebila, 3.64 at Nafoun and 3.76 at both sites. These results indicated that these sites shows moderately diversity (3 bits <math>H' < 4</math> bits). The Piélou's Equitability index was 0.80 for the site of Tiebila and 0.84 for Nafoun; combining the two sites gave a value of 0.82. No significant difference was found for the two parameters of floristic diversity between the two sites (Table 1). At the plot level, the values of the Shannon index was found to be 1.57 ± 0.67 in the grass savannah, and 2.40 ± 0.42 in cleared forest. The coefficient of equitability of Piélou varied between 0.77 ± 0.23 (grassy savannah) and 0.84 ± 0.11 (savannah with trees) (Table 2). When considering vegetation type, the Shannon index was between 3 and 4 bits for woodland, savannah and shrub savanna. This result indicated that these formations showed medium floristic diversity while a low diversity ($H < 3$ bits) was found in grassy savannah and bush fallow. The Shannon index was significantly different ($P = 0,039$) among vegetation type while the Piélou index did not show any significant difference (Table 2).

Figure 3: Proportion of species surveyed by families around apiaries

Floristic similarity

The two inventoried sites have in common 51 species, 46 genera, and 24 families. The similarity coefficient of Jaccard was 53.13% while Sorensen similarity coefficient was 69.39%. These results indicated that the two study sites have the same floristic background.

DISCUSSION

The floristic richness of 96 species was significantly lower than the 121 ligneous species found by Coulibaly *et al.* (2013) in the immediate vicinity of an apiary located in the forest-savanna transition zone in Côte d'Ivoire. However, this value was higher than the 60 woody species encountered in the Ngazobil reserve in western Senegal, in dry tropical Sudano-Sahelian climate (Diatta *et al.*, 2009). Abourhamane *et al.* (2013) found a lower value, 31 woody species in the Dan Kada Dodo-Dan Gado classified forest complex located in south-central Niger under Sahelian dry tropical climate. Climatic differences which may impact the development of woody species may explain these differences.

Fabaceae, Rubiaceae and Combretaceae were the richest species families in the environment of the two apiaries. Concerning the Fabaceae family, the obtained results were similar to those of Soro (2014) who found that Fabaceae was the family most represented in the woody flora of northern Côte d'Ivoire. An inventory done by Ouattara (2017) in the Department of Bondoukou (North-East of Côte d'Ivoire), indicated also that Fabaceae was the richest. The high number of species belonging to Fabaceae family, particularly those of the subfamily Mimosoideae, and of the Combretaceae was characteristic of a generally dry climate (Aubreville, 1950). This importance of these families was also due to the mode of dissemination of species (Abourhamane *et al.*, 2013). The seeds of Combretaceae are winged therefore, they are easily disseminated by wind. Besides that, Fabaceae are generally used as fodder so that their seeds are easily spread by zoochoria. This domination of Fabaceae and Combretaceae was also noted by Tahirou *et al.* (2016) in the rural district of Tanda in southwestern Niger.

Concerning the family of Rubiaceae, a higher number of species (22 species) was found by Tiébré *et al.* (2016) in the Sudanese zone of Côte d'Ivoire. This result compared to ours could be explained by the size of the study areas. In this study, the area of inventory was 157 ha whereas it was about 21 728 ha in that of Tiébré *et al.* (2016). In addition, their study took into account both woody and herbaceous species whereas our study took into account only woody species.

The value of 3.76 bits found for the Shannon index ($3 < H' < 4$) indicated the presence of a moderately diversified flora. This value is lower than the 3.93 bits found by Coulibaly *et al.* (2013) around an apiary located in the forest-savanna transition zone in Côte d'Ivoire. This value was far superior to the 2.34 bits found by Abourhamane *et al.* (2013) at the Dan Kada Dodo-Dan Gado classified forest complex in South Central Niger.

With the exception of the Piélou index, all the floristic diversity parameters considered in this study were significantly different among type of vegetation. At plot level, the species richness varies from 7.50 ± 2.12 in grassland savannah to 21.14 ± 7.06 in open forest. The number of families found varied from 5.50 ± 2.12 in grassy savannah to 11.57 ± 4.28 in open forest. The Shannon index was determined to be between 1.57 ± 0.67 in grass savannah and 2.40 ± 0.42 in open forest. The weakest Piélou equitability index (0.74 bits) was obtained in the degraded zone (fallows). The high values of this index observed both at the site and type of vegetation levels reflected a good regularity of the species. The absence of a significant difference in this index indicated a homogeneous distribution of the flora in the different types of vegetation. According to Coulibaly *et al.* (2013), this situation is partly due to the predominance of "generalist" species, which are therefore common to all types of vegetation.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that the woody vegetation around the apiaries installed in Badenou classified forest, was moderately diversified. The two sites presents the same floristic background. A total of 96 species grouped into 72 genera and 30 families were inventoried. The value obtained for the Shannon index was 3.76 bits. The listed species were regularly spread over all the sites indicated by a Piélou's equitability index of 0.82 bits. Considering that this woody flora is potentially melliferous, the determined floristic characteristics indicated a good asset for intensive beekeeping in this forest. This vegetation could provide abundant and varied floral resources to bees. Nevertheless, this study should also take into account herbaceous plants to be complete and more useful to beekeeping.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the Director of the National protected forests (SODEFOR) and the Coordinator in the Northern Center (Korhogo) for accepting the completion of this study in Badenou protected forest.

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